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Title:	Linked Open Samian Ware – AMT Perspective
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LINKED OPEN SAMIAN WARE – AMT PERSPECTIVE

Linked Open Samian Ware provides the documentation to the SPARQL-Query Editor for the **Samian Research Database**.

As a result of a cooperation agreement between the universities of Reading and Leeds together with the Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum Mainz, the life-long study made by Brian Hartley and Brenda Dickinson of the stamps and signatures on samian became available as a database. They were originally published as a series of books (Institute of Classical Studies, London, from 2008 onwards).

The **Samian Research Database** comprises a suite of databases concerned with samian ware. Their aim is to standardize the recording and publishing of samian ware in such a way that the data is available both for comparative identification, and more significantly for scientific analysis using statistical and mapping tools. All have their individual search masks appropriate to the questions likely to require resolution. The databases comprise the following:

- Names on Terra Sigillata / Corpus Vasorum Arretinorum (merged into one database)
- Name marked decorated vessels
- Ovolo Vessels

ONTOLOGY

PREFIXES

Linked Open Samian Ware features several preestablished prefixes as well as the prefix *lado* and *samian*.

Prefix	Value
samian	http://lod.archaeology.link/data/samian/
crm	http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/
dc	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/
dct	http://purl.org/dc/terms/
dcmitype	http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/
geosparql	">http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
lado	http://samian/ontology
owl	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#
xsd	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#
rdf	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
rdfs	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
sf	http://www.opengis.net/ont/sf#
skos	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#
xml	http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace

INFORMATION CARRIER

ACTOR

LOCATION

POTFORM

AMT-MODEL

The data contains strings with vague expressions. This vagueness is modelled using the Academic Meta Tool. The AMT-Model depends on the keywords **AND** ($AMT\text{-weight} = 1$) and **OR** ($AMT\text{-weight}/2$).

Attributions for e.g. productionscenters can result in more than one place, which has to be recorded accordingly. This vagueness has been taken into consideration with the Linked Open Samian Ware Project.

In the following examples the relations for the potter Quietus/Quetus (ae_5889), his production centres as well as the information carrier 118117 (ic_118117) are mapped.

AMT-MODEL EXAMPLES

EXAMPLE: ACTOR ENTITY & PRODUCTION CENTRE

Samian AMT-Model for the potter **Quietus/Quetus (ae_5889)** and the productioncentre **Rheinzabern (loc_pc_2000047)**:

Example Query: Filter all weights for the Potter Quietus' Productioncentres:

The String containing the necessary data reads as follows "Kräherwald and Rheinzabern"

```
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
```

```
PREFIX lato: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
```

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
```

```
PREFIX amt: <http://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab#>
```

```
PREFIX samian: <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/>
```

```
SELECT ?subject ?subjectLabel ?predicateLabel ?objectLabel ?weight WHERE {  
  ?subject lato:hasAMT ?amt.  
  ?amt rdf:subject ?subject.  
  ?subject rdfs:label ?subjectLabel.  
  ?amt rdf:predicate ?predicate.
```

```

?predicate rdfs:label ?predicateLabel.
?amt rdf:object ?object.
?object rdfs:label ?objectLabel.
?amt amt:weight ?weight.
FILTER(?subject = samian:ae_5889)
FILTER(?predicate = lado:worksAtPlace)
FILTER (lang(?predicateLabel) = 'en')
}

```

Output:

subject	subjectLabel	predicateLabel	objectLabel	weight
samian:ae_5889	"Quietus (Quetus)"@en	"works at place"@en	"Kräherwald"@en	1
samian:ae_5889	"Quietus (Quetus)"@en	"works at place"@en	"Rheinzabern"@en	1

→ Quietus worked at Kräherwald AND Rheinzabern, so the weight results in 1

EXAMPLE: INSCRIPTION CARRIER & PRODUCTION CENTRE

Samian AMT-Model for **information carrier 118117 (ic_118117)** and the productioncentre **Rheinzabern (loc_pc_2000047)**:

Example Query: Filter all weights for the Kilnsites of Information Carrier 118117:

The String containing the necessary data reads as follows "Kräherwald and Rheinzabern"

```
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX lado: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX amt: <http://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab#>
PREFIX samian: <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/>

SELECT ?subject ?subjectLabel ?predicateLabel ?objectLabel ?weight WHERE {
  ?subject lado:hasAMT ?amt.
  ?amt rdf:subject ?subject.
  ?subject rdfs:label ?subjectLabel.
  ?amt rdf:predicate ?predicate.
  ?predicate rdfs:label ?predicateLabel.
  ?amt rdf:object ?object.
  ?object rdfs:label ?objectLabel.
  ?amt amt:weight ?weight.
  FILTER(?subject = samian:ic_118117)
  FILTER(?predicate = lado:hasKilnsite)
  FILTER (lang(?predicateLabel) = 'en')
}
```

Output:

subject	subjectLabel	predicateLabel	objectLabel	weight
samian:ic_118117	"redslipvessel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"has kilnsite"@en	"Kräherwald"@en	1
samian:ic_118117	"redslipvessel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"has kilnsite"@en	"Rheinzabern"@en	1

→ The Informationcarrier's Productioncentre has been attributed to Kräherwald AND Rheinzabern, so the weight results in 1

EXAMPLE: INSCRIPTION CARRIER & POTFORM

Samian AMT-Model for **information carrier 118117 (ic_118117)** and the potform **18 (pf_9)**:

Example Query: Filter all weights for the potforms of Information Carrier 118117:

The String containing the necessary data reads as follows "15/17 or 18 or 18/31"

```
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX lado: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX amt: <http://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab#>
PREFIX samian: <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/>
```

```
SELECT ?subject ?subjectLabel ?predicateLabel ?objectLabel ?weight WHERE {
  ?subject lado:hasAMT ?amt.
  ?amt rdf:subject ?subject.
  ?subject rdfs:label ?subjectLabel.
  ?amt rdf:predicate ?predicate.
  ?predicate rdfs:label ?predicateLabel.
  ?amt rdf:object ?object.
  ?object rdfs:label ?objectLabel.
  ?amt amt:weight ?weight.
  FILTER(?subject = samian:ic_118117)
```

```

FILTER(?predicate = lado:representedBy)
FILTER (lang(?predicateLabel) = 'en')
}

```

Output:

subject	subjectLabel	predicateLabel	objectLabel	weight
samian:ic_118117	"redslipvessel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"represented by"@en	"15/17"	0.330000013
samian:ic_118117	"redslipvessel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"represented by"@en	"18"	0.330000013
samian:ic_118117	"redslipvessel formtype 15/17 or 18 or 18/31"@en	"represented by"@en	"18/31"	0.330000013

→ The Informationcarriers either has the potform 15/17, 18 OR 18/31 (vagueness), so each weight results in 0.33